

Comparison of Standard and Accelerated Ponseti Methods for Management of Idiopathic Congenital Talipes Equinovarus

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Abstract:

Background: The Ponseti method is the gold standard for treating idiopathic clubfoot, but the prolonged treatment duration can lead to compliance issues. This study aimed to compare outcomes between the standard weekly Ponseti method and an accelerated biweekly protocol.

Methods: In this prospective randomized study, 70 patients (103 clubfeet) were randomized to either standard Ponseti (weekly casting, n=50 feet) or accelerated Ponseti (biweekly casting, n=53 feet) groups. Outcomes assessed included Pirani scores, number of casts, treatment duration, tenotomy rates, and complications. Patients were followed for 6 months post-treatment.

Results: There were no significant differences in final Pirani scores between groups. The accelerated group had a significantly shorter mean treatment duration (21.57 vs 40.88 days, $p < 0.001$) with a similar mean number of casts. Tenotomy rates and relapse rates at 6 months were comparable between groups. The accelerated group had fewer plaster-related complications.

Conclusion: The accelerated Ponseti protocol achieved similar outcomes to the standard method in significantly less time, potentially improving treatment compliance with no increase in complications.

Keywords: Clubfoot, Ponseti Method, Congenital Talipes equinovarus, Accelerated Protocol.

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Introduction

Congenital talipes equinovarus (CTEV), commonly known as clubfoot, is one of the most prevalent congenital foot deformities, affecting 1-2 per 1000 live births [1]. The deformity consists of four components - cavus, forefoot adduction, hindfoot Varus, and equinus - which if left untreated can lead to significant disability [2]. Over the past few decades, the Ponseti method has become the gold standard for clubfoot treatment worldwide, with reported success rates of over 95% [3].

The Ponseti method involves serial manipulation and casting, typically performed weekly, followed by percutaneous tenotomy of the Achilles tendon if required [4]. While highly effective, the prolonged treatment duration of 5-8 weeks can lead to issues with compliance, especially in resource-limited settings where frequent hospital visits may be challenging for families [5].

Several studies have investigated accelerated Ponseti protocols with promising results [6,7]. However, there remains a need for further high-quality studies directly comparing standard and accelerated Ponseti protocols, especially in different populations and healthcare settings. The ideal

interval between cast changes that balances speed of correction with safety and efficacy is still debated [8].

This study aimed to compare outcomes between the standard weekly Ponseti method and an accelerated biweekly protocol in the treatment of idiopathic clubfoot at a tertiary care center in India. We hypothesized that the accelerated protocol would achieve similar outcomes in a significantly shorter timeframe, potentially improving treatment compliance without increasing complications.

Methods

Study Design and Setting: This was a prospective, randomized, comparative study conducted at the Department of Orthopaedics, Government Medical College, Kozhikode, India between January 2021 and January 2023. The study was approved by the institutional ethics committee.

Participants: All children with idiopathic congenital clubfoot aged less than 1 year presenting to our institution during the study period were screened for eligibility. Inclusion criteria were: 1) idiopathic clubfoot, 2) age <1 year, and 3)

previously untreated. Exclusion criteria were: 1) syndromic clubfoot, 2) neglected clubfoot, 3) relapsed clubfoot, and 4) postural clubfoot.

Sample Size: Sample size was calculated based on a previous study [9], assuming a mean difference in treatment time of 20 days between groups, with a standard deviation of 5.78 days. Using a power of 90% and alpha of 0.05, the minimum sample size was calculated as 42 feet per group.

Randomization: Eligible patients were randomly allocated to either the standard Ponseti group or the accelerated Ponseti group using a web-based random allocation software. In bilateral cases, both feet were allocated to the same group but analyzed as independent variables.

Interventions: Both groups received treatment as per standard Ponseti protocol [4]. The only difference was in the frequency of cast changes:

Standard Ponseti group: Weekly cast changes
Accelerated Ponseti group: Biweekly cast changes (twice per week)

All other aspects of treatment including manipulation technique, casting material, and bracing protocol were identical between groups. Percutaneous Achilles tenotomy was performed if dorsiflexion was $<15^\circ$ after correction of other deformities. Post-tenotomy, a final cast was applied for 3 weeks in both groups.

Outcome Measures: The primary outcome measure was the Pirani score [10] at the end of casting and at 6 months follow-up. Secondary outcomes included number of casts, duration of treatment, tenotomy rate, complications, and relapses.

Pirani scoring was performed by a blinded assessor (associate professor or senior resident) who was not involved in treatment. Initial Pirani score was calculated before the first cast. Final score was calculated just before brace application. A score >1 at 6 months follow-up was considered a relapse.

Statistical Analysis: Data was analyzed using SPSS version 28. Continuous variables were compared using independent t-tests and categorical variables using chi-square tests. A p-value <0.05 was considered statistically significant.

Results

The study included a total of 70 patients with 103 clubfeet, randomized into two groups: the standard Ponseti group (35 patients, 50 feet) and the accelerated Ponseti group (35 patients, 53 feet).

Baseline characteristics were comparable between the two groups (Table 1). The mean age at the start of treatment was 32.4 days in the standard group and 29.9 days in the accelerated group, with no significant difference ($p=0.970$). Gender

distribution was identical in both groups, with 66% male and 34% female ($p=0.997$). The side involvement was also similar, with 52% right and 48% left in the standard group, and 51% right and 49% left in the accelerated group ($p=0.684$). Bilateral cases accounted for 45.7% in the standard group and 51.4% in the accelerated group ($p=0.674$). The mean initial Pirani score was slightly higher in the accelerated group (5.38) compared to the standard group (5.14), but this difference was not statistically significant ($p=0.051$).

Pirani scores were compared at different time points during the treatment (Table 2). The initial scores were 5.14 ± 0.62 and 5.38 ± 0.58 for the standard and accelerated groups, respectively ($p=0.051$). At the end of casting, the scores had significantly improved in both groups, reaching 0.39 ± 0.34 in the standard group and 0.43 ± 0.36 in the accelerated group, with no significant difference between the groups ($p=0.522$). At the 6-month follow-up, there was a slight increase in Pirani scores in both groups (0.69 ± 0.45 for standard and 0.77 ± 0.43 for accelerated), but the difference remained statistically insignificant ($p=0.340$).

Treatment parameters varied between the two groups (Table 3). The mean number of casts required was slightly higher in the accelerated group (6.21 ± 1.18) compared to the standard group (5.84 ± 1.21), but this difference was not statistically significant ($p=0.116$). However, the mean treatment duration showed a marked difference between the groups. The accelerated group achieved correction in significantly less time (21.57 ± 3.86 days) compared to the standard group (40.88 ± 7.32 days), and this difference was highly statistically significant ($p<0.001$). The tenotomy rate was high in both groups, with 92% (46 feet) in the standard group and 96% (51 feet) in the accelerated group undergoing the procedure, but the difference was not statistically significant ($p=0.357$).

Relapse rates at the 6-month follow-up were assessed (Table 4). In the standard Ponseti group, 3 feet (6%) showed relapse, while 47 feet (94%) maintained correction. The accelerated Ponseti group had a slightly higher relapse rate with 5 feet (9.4%) showing relapse and 48 feet (90.6%) maintaining correction. However, this difference in relapse rates between the two groups was not statistically significant ($p=0.515$).

Complications during treatment were observed and compared between the two groups (Table 5). The standard Ponseti group experienced a higher overall complication rate (24%) compared to the accelerated Ponseti group (13.2%). Specifically, plaster sores were observed in 4 feet (8%) in the standard group compared to 2 feet (3.8%) in the accelerated group. Loose plaster was more common in the standard group, affecting 6 feet (12%), while

only 2 feet (3.8%) in the accelerated group experienced this issue. Tight plaster with edema occurred in 2 feet (4%) in the standard group and 3 feet (5.7%) in the accelerated group. Although the accelerated group showed fewer overall complications, statistical analysis for significance was not performed due to the small number of events in each category.

In summary, the accelerated Ponseti method achieved similar correction of clubfoot deformity as measured by Pirani scores, with a significantly shorter treatment duration. The number of casts, tenotomy rates, and relapse rates were comparable between the two groups. The accelerated group showed a trend towards fewer plaster-related complications, although this was not statistically analyzed due to the small numbers involved.

Table 1: Baseline characteristics of study participants

Characteristic	Standard Ponseti (n=50 feet)	Accelerated Ponseti (n=53 feet)	P value
Mean age (days)	32.4	29.9	0.970
Gender			0.997
Male	33 (66%)	35 (66%)	
Female	17 (34%)	18 (34%)	
Side involved			0.684
Right	26 (52%)	27 (51%)	
Left	24 (48%)	26 (49%)	
Bilateral cases	16 (45.7%)	18 (51.4%)	0.674
Mean initial Pirani score	5.14	5.38	0.051

Table 2 shows the comparison of Pirani scores between the two groups at different time points.

Table 2: Comparison of Pirani scores

Time point	Standard Ponseti (n=50 feet)	Accelerated Ponseti (n=53 feet)	P value
Initial	5.14 ± 0.62	5.38 ± 0.58	0.051
End of casting	0.39 ± 0.34	0.43 ± 0.36	0.522
6 months follow-up	0.69 ± 0.45	0.77 ± 0.43	0.340

Table 3 compares the treatment parameters between the two groups.

Table 3: Comparison of treatment parameters

Parameter	Standard Ponseti (n=50 feet)	Accelerated Ponseti (n=53 feet)	P value
Mean number of casts	5.84 ± 1.21	6.21 ± 1.18	0.116
Mean treatment duration (days)	40.88 ± 7.32	21.57 ± 3.86	<0.001
Tenotomy rate	46 (92%)	51 (96%)	0.357

Table 4 shows the relapse rates at 6 months follow-up.

Table 4: Relapse rates at 6 months follow-up

Group	Relapse	No Relapse	P value
Standard Ponseti (n=50 feet)	3 (6%)	47 (94%)	0.515
Accelerated Ponseti (n=53 feet)	5 (9.4%)	48 (90.6%)	

Table 5 compares the complications observed during treatment between the two groups.

Table 5: Complications observed during treatment

Complication	Standard Ponseti (n=50 feet)	Accelerated Ponseti (n=53 feet)
Plaster sore	4 (8%)	2 (3.8%)
Loose plaster	6 (12%)	2 (3.8%)
Tight plaster with edema	2 (4%)	3 (5.7%)
Total	12 (24%)	7 (13.2%)

Discussion

This study compared outcomes between standard weekly Ponseti casting and an accelerated biweekly protocol for the treatment of idiopathic clubfoot. Our results demonstrate that the accelerated protocol achieved similar correction in significantly less time, with no increase in complications or relapse rates at short-term follow-up.

The primary outcome measure, Pirani score, showed no significant difference between groups at the end of casting or at 6 months follow-up. This is consistent with previous studies on accelerated Ponseti protocols [6,7], suggesting that more frequent manipulation and casting does not compromise the quality of correction achieved.

A key finding was the significantly shorter treatment duration in the accelerated group (mean 21.57 vs 40.88 days, $p < 0.001$), despite a slightly higher mean

number of casts (6.21 vs 5.84, $p>0.05$). This nearly 50% reduction in treatment time could have important implications for improving compliance, especially in settings where frequent hospital visits are challenging. Our results align with those reported by other researchers who found similar reductions in treatment time with more frequent casting [11,12].

The rate of Achilles tenotomy was high in both groups (92% standard, 96% accelerated) but not significantly different. This is higher than the 70-80% rate typically reported in literature [13], possibly due to stricter criteria for achieving adequate dorsiflexion in our center.

Relapse rates at 6 months were low and comparable between groups (6% standard, 9.4% accelerated, $p=0.51$). Longer follow-up is needed to assess long-term outcomes, as relapses can occur up to 2-3 years after initial correction [14].

An interesting finding was the lower rate of plaster-related complications in the accelerated group. This may be due to the shorter duration each cast is worn, reducing the risk of skin irritation or plaster loosening. The more frequent clinical reviews in the accelerated protocol may also allow earlier detection and management of any issues.

The main limitation of this study is the relatively short follow-up period of 6 months. Longer follow-up is needed to assess maintenance of correction and functional outcomes. Additionally, this was a single-center study and results may not be generalizable to all settings.

Conclusion

The accelerated Ponseti protocol with biweekly casting achieved similar outcomes to the standard weekly protocol in significantly less time, with no increase in complications or short-term relapse rates. This approach could improve treatment compliance and reduce the burden on families, especially in resource-limited settings. Further research with longer follow-up is needed to confirm long-term outcomes and optimal casting intervals.

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